

What the Salt Crystals Knew

Desert, Extraction, and Poetic Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

In a time when the climate crisis accelerates into full gear, the so-called “green transition” reveals itself as another failed project of modernity. Far from dismantling extractivism, it expands its frontiers into new territories under the promise of sustainability. The lithium rush in the South American salt flats—lands portrayed as barren, desolate, and “empty”—exemplifies this paradox. *What the Salt Crystals Knew*, a video-animation filmed in the Mascalín salt flats of San Juan, Argentina, explores this terrain both materially and symbolically. The work questions the historical construction of “the desert” as a category of emptiness and barbarism, a colonial trope that justified territorial conquest and continues to authorize extractive projects under ecological pretexts. This paper situates *What the Salt Crystals Knew* within the intertwined histories of environmental transformation, colonial expansion, and artistic inquiry. Through poetic knowledge, it proposes an alternative epistemology to the scientific and technocratic rationalities that perceive the world as inert matter. Reframing the desert not as absence but as a living field of relations, *What the Salt Crystals Knew* invites a renewed encounter with environments systematically misrepresented as void. The desert, once defined by lack, emerges instead as a site of planetary knowledge—where salt crystals remember what progress has tried to forget.

Keywords

Lithium Extraction, Green Colonialism, Desert Imaginaries, Poetic knowledge, Decolonial Ecology, Cosmotronics, Andean Salt Flats, Artistic Research

1 Terraforming the Desert: Lithium, Green Energy, and the Failed Promise of Sustainability

The planetary shift toward “green energy” has become one of the most powerful narratives of the twenty-first century. Politicians, corporations, and even environmental movements frame the electrification of mobility and the expansion of renewable technologies as the key to overcoming the fossil-fueled Anthropocene. Yet beneath this veneer of ecological salvation, the logics of extraction remain unchanged. The promise of a sustainable future reproduces the same patterns of occupation, dispossession, and accumulation that structured the first wave of industrial modernity.

In Latin America, the lithium triangle - comprising Argentina, Bolivia, and Chile - has emerged as the epicenter of this new scramble for resources. Once deemed useless or “unproductive”, the Andean salt flats are now seen as planetary batteries, repositories of “white gold” indispensable for electric vehicles and digital infrastructures. As Thea Riofrancos has argued, lithium extraction encapsulates the contradictions of “green extractivism”, where “renewable” technologies depend on destructive mining practices that perpetuate colonial dependencies [1].

The Mascalín salt flats in San Juan, Argentina, where *What the Salt Crystals Knew* was filmed, embody this transformation. Recently acquired by an international conglomerate for lithium extraction, this territory is being reconfigured both physically and symbolically. The process of extraction literally redesigns the landscape: vast grids of turquoise evaporation pools cut through the reflective white crust, transforming the desert into an

industrial surface of chemical production. These pools are the contemporary descendants of colonial geometries - the same rational lines used to enclose, measure, and exploit land in the name of progress.

What is at stake is not only ecological devastation but an epistemic violence: the continued representation of the salt flats as “empty lands” awaiting productive use. The modern history of deserts, then, is inseparable from the history of their representation. Through cartography, photography, and scientific surveying, deserts have been visualized as spaces of absence - blank maps upon which modernity could inscribe its fantasies of control. As T.J. Demos and Macarena Gómez-Barris remind us, “extraction is not only material but also epistemic” [2]. The desert’s portrayal as an inert backdrop legitimizes its occupation by those who claim to bring life to it.

In *What the Salt Crystals Knew*, this myth is dismantled through slowness, shimmering textures, and non-linear temporality. The camera lingers on salt surfaces that flicker with light and crystalline growth, revealing the desert not as void but as an active geological and spiritual organism. The film’s title suggests this inversion: the salt crystals *know* - they remember the histories of evaporation, of colonial surveying, of the environmental consequences that accumulate silently beneath the crust.

2 Civilization and Barbarism: The Colonial Construction of the Desert

The concept of the “desert” in Argentina is not only geographical but deeply political. In the nineteenth century, it became the central metaphor of the nation’s project of modernization. When Domingo Faustino Sarmiento wrote in *Facundo: Civilization and Barbarism* (1845) that “the evil that plagues the Argentine Republic is its extension: the desert surrounds it on all sides” [3], he articulated a vision of geography as destiny. For Sarmiento and his contemporaries, the desert symbolized disorder, barbarism, and backwardness - everything that stood in the way of the nation’s alignment with Europe. To conquer the desert was thus to conquer barbarism itself.

This rhetoric provided the ideological foundation for state campaigns of expansion and extermination. The so-called “Conquest of the Desert”, led by General Julio Argentino Roca in the 1870s and 1880s, was in fact a genocidal campaign against Indigenous nations of

Patagonia and the Pampas. Under the pretext of civilizing an empty land, the Argentine state dispossessed thousands of Mapuche, Ranquel, and Tehuelche people from their ancestral territories [4]. The “desert”, far from being uninhabited, was made empty through military violence. The term’s power resided precisely in its fiction: by naming a space as void, one could erase the histories and cosmologies that animated it.

In this sense, the modern desert functions as what anthropologist Gastón Gordillo calls a “negative geography” - a terrain defined by absence but produced through violent presence [5]. Its emptiness is manufactured, its silence enforced. *What the Salt Crystals Knew* engages this history by returning to the scene of erasure. Filmed on land recently acquired by extractive capital, the work renders visible the paradox of a desert that is both overexploited and underrepresented. Through visual and sonic textures, it resists the colonial lens that flattens the landscape into mere scenery.

Moreover, the work connects the nineteenth-century discourse of “civilization and barbarism” with contemporary extractivism. The rhetoric of progress persists, though it has changed costume. Where the state once spoke of “civilizing the frontier”, corporations now speak of “sustainable development” and “green energy”. Both rely on a common epistemology: that of a world divided between productive centers and expendable peripheries. The Argentine desert, once the site of military conquest, becomes the site of technocratic conquest - what Gómez-Barris terms “the extractive zone” [6].

To read *What the Salt Crystals Knew* through this lineage is to understand that lithium extraction is not simply an environmental issue but a continuation of colonial world-making. The salt flat’s alleged emptiness, its “desertness”, functions as a cover for the ongoing expropriation of planetary futures. The film counters this by producing what Édouard Glissant calls “opacity”: an aesthetic that resists transparency, that refuses to be fully known or commodified [7]. Its poetics of trembling, its slow temporality, its refusal of narrative mastery - all work against the extractive gaze.

3 Poetic Knowledge and the Agency of Matter

“Poetic knowledge”, writes Aimé Césaire, “is born in the great silence of scientific knowledge” [8]. In that silence lies the possibility of another way of knowing the world - one that does not reduce it to object or resource but encounters it as relation. *What the Salt Crystals Knew* operates precisely in this interval. Against the distant gaze of science and the instrumental logic of industry, it proposes a sensorial, embodied, and affective mode of attention. To see the desert not as inert matter but as a sentient field requires a shift from observation to participation - from voyeurism to coexistence.

This epistemic shift challenges the long history of Western thought that separated humans from nature, mind from matter, culture from landscape. The Enlightenment’s dream of objectivity produced what Bruno Latour called “the view from nowhere”: a detached spectator surveying the world as if from behind glass [9]. It is this very posture that enables extraction, for it conceives of the Earth as a passive object awaiting human intervention. The desert, viewed through this optic, is the ultimate screen for projection - empty, silent, compliant.

Poetic knowledge interrupts this regime of seeing. It asks us to listen, to attune, to sense the murmurs of the nonhuman. In the Mascañ salt flats, every grain of salt is a sensor recording centuries of evaporation and deposition. The land itself performs a slow choreography of transformation, a material intelligence far exceeding human scales of time. To acknowledge this is to recognize, as Eduardo Kohn suggests in *How Forests Think*, that “life thinks” beyond the human [10]. The desert thinks through salt and wind; it dreams in the language of reflection and refraction.

In this light, *What the Salt Crystals Knew* can be understood as a form of “decolonial ecology”. It neither romanticizes nature nor aestheticizes ruin; rather, it reclaims the desert as a cosmological interlocutor. By engaging with Indigenous and Andean understandings of land as animate, the work aligns with what Marisol de la Cadena terms “earth-beings” - entities that are simultaneously geological and political [11]. The salt crystal, shimmering under the camera’s gaze, becomes an agent of knowledge, a witness to the intertwined histories of colonization and resistance.

The poetic thus becomes political. In refusing the linear time of progress, the film unsettles the

epistemologies that underwrite extraction. Its temporality - slow, cyclical, uncertain - echoes the rhythms of the Earth rather than the accelerations of capital. The silence that permeates its images is not emptiness but fullness: the hum of a world that continues to speak despite centuries of silencing. As the West remains obsessed with commodifying and controlling nature, *What the Salt Crystals Knew* reminds us, as Latour noted, that “nature is not this inert, passive object of appropriation - it’s a subject with its own agency” [12].

In the end, the desert is not a void to be filled but a mirror held up to modernity’s illusions. What the salt crystals know is that progress is not salvation but sediment; that every act of extraction leaves behind a residue of memory. To attend to that residue is to begin the work of repair - to imagine an ecology of relation rather than exploitation, of listening rather than speaking for. Through poetic knowledge, we might learn once again to stand with the desert, not over it.

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